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Printed Materials (release 1) D6.6

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a short overview of the production of all print and presentation materials that will be used for the communication and dissemination of Q-SORT. It follows *Q-SORT D6.3 Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan including graphic design guidelines (releases 1-2)*. All future printed materials for Q-SORT will be based on the designs and templates described in this document. Printed materials play a key role in dissemination and communication, as the first impression one gets of the project, which cannot be undone, is imparted by them.

This document comprises four chapters.

Chapter 1 is a short introduction.

Chapter 2 provides a brief overview of the philosophy and process that were followed in designing the dissemination materials.

Chapter 3 provides low-resolution copies of the above designs.

Chapter 4 sums up the conclusions and take-home messages that were gleaned through this work.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS AND THIS DELIVERABLE?

Within Q-SORT the dissemination and communication materials are tools that will be used by:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Particularly by the staff responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, as this is a public document and is available on the project's website, it will be accessible by external parties interested in disseminating and communicating Q-SORT.

This deliverable will be updated periodically at a later phase of the project according to the project's needs.

2 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

The design of the printed materials was based on two simple but effective requirements: we aimed to define a graphic identity that is at the same time distinctive and classic. Achieving both a degree of timelessness and a striking design that 'speaks to everyone' has in turn two significant consequences.

A timeless and classic look means that the design is conceived to 'age well'.

On the other hand, a strong graphic statement that is simple, easy to identify, and based on universal proportions (such as for instance certain mathematical ratios) allows the use of the same design/theme for both dissemination and communication. This strong visual identity was consistently 'declined' it in the various print designs, as detailed in the next paragraph.

Both considerations translate into cost and labour savings for the project, especially with a view to its future upkeep/sustainability.

Another cost-saving consideration was the idea of designing templates for brochures and posters that the partners will be able to easily fill in and print locally as the need arises (see below).

3 LIST OF THE DESIGNS THAT WERE PRODUCED

In terms of printed materials for dissemination and communication, the needs of such an ambitious project as Q-SORT are many. Broadly speaking, some printed assets are meant to be general-purpose, i.e. deployable anywhere, whilst others are event-specific, i.e. tailored to each specific Q-SORT International Conference. Based on the project schedule as well as on an evaluation of the overall progress so far (and in particular on DE6.3), the following assets were thus identified and then designed:

1. foldable three-sided general-purpose A4 Project brochure;
2. template for conference-specific A2 Project poster;
3. general-purpose 80x200 Project vinyl banner;
4. template for conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts;
5. general-purpose Q-SORT-branded tote bag;
6. template for Q-SORT slides.

1) General-purpose three-fold A4 brochure, to be deployed at various events as a general presentation of the project. The choice of a standard ISO 216 / DIN format instead of more 'fashionable' ones translates

into savings for the project and in no way diminishes the impact of the design. The standard small format also makes it easy to arrange for local and/or future additional print runs.

2) Template for event-specific vertical A2 poster, printable as A3 if necessary. The same considerations as above are valid regarding ISO 216 / DIN. A2 was chosen as the largest possible format that can be hung without too much trouble in pinboards and public spaces – since, trivially, a larger format guarantees greater visibility. The design is compatible with printing in A3, which is significantly cheaper for small runs of digital prints.

3) General-purpose 80x200 standalone vinyl banner, to advertise and signal events taking place in a specific venue, such as conferences, seminars, lectures, press conferences, etc. The choice of PVC as the printing material makes the roll-up banner suitable for outdoor use as well.

4) Template for the conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts / Conference Proceedings, which has three functions:

- it provides readers with abstracts for all the topics of all the talks and all the posters presented at the conference;
- it provides a list of all participants with their contact details;
- it is also meant as a memento of the conference for all participants.

5) General-purpose Q-SORT-branded tote bag, to be given to all conference participants as well as to guests.

6) Template for Q-SORT slide presentations. To be used by all partners when presenting on behalf of Q-SORT. A set of coherent graphic rules is given in the template.

The new designs were initially showcased at the [First Q-SORT International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time](#). A first run of 1500 brochures, 10 A2 posters and one vinyl banner was deployed on that occasion, during which it was evident that the strong, sober Q-SORT designs made the project stand out, given the generally formless and cluttered designs with which science projects and events are generally publicised. Posters and brochures that were not picked up by visitors were split between FZJ and CNR for future redeployment.

Insofar as possible, Q-SORT designs are being printed locally by partners, close to where they are meant to be deployed, in order to save on expenses and environmental impact. These designs are sent to partners with specific instructions as to the type of printing process, paper, and finish to be adopted, so as to ensure a consistently high standard of quality.

All the designs were optimised for offset printing but can be output as high-quality laser or inkjet prints if necessary.

3.1 THE ACTUAL DESIGN PROCESS

The design process started from the idea of animating the Project Logo, described in *D6.1 - Project Website and Logo (first release)* and in *D6.5 - Project Website and Logo (second release)*. We developed and explored several possibilities for the animation studies made for the logo until we reached a satisfying version, which we used as a leitmotiv throughout. Having settled on the main graphic element and proportions, special care was taken in considering the interplay of the design with the type of paper and of printing method chosen for each of the intended formats. Then we proceeded to consistently 'decline' the leitmotiv in the various designs. For each asset we explored different combination of colours, playing with

the same black/white/red palette. In the specific case of the A2 poster, two versions were issued since the hosting partner liked to use them both.

Throughout the design phase, all the guidelines regarding the use of the various official logos were observed.

3.2 COPYWRITING

Similar considerations of simplicity and efficacy were adopted for the copywriting. The latter, insofar as possible, eschewed lingo in favour of clear and simple explanations, understandable by the general public, but also providing meaningful information for specialists. The text can be read from Figure 2 in the next chapter.

Figure 2: General-purpose three-fold A4 brochure (inner fold)

International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time

Monday 27 – Wednesday 30
May, 2018

Zentralbibliothek - Building 04.7
Forschungszentrum Jülich
Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse
52428 Jülich, Germany

qsort.eu

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Figure 4a: Conference-specific vertical poster - white background

Figure 4b: Conference-specific vertical poster - black background

Figure 5: General-purpose 80x200 stand-alone vinyl banner

Figure 6: General-purpose tote bag

5 CONCLUSIONS

We think the results show the benefit of involving professionals with the right profile in the design and copywriting process.

Suitable 'buffer time' needs to be scheduled between completion of the designs to the coordinator's and designers' satisfaction, and their final delivery. This is in order to take into account possible changes at the request of partners or of those institutions whose logo is included in the design. The number and duration of these 'refinement iterations' seems to grow exponentially with the number of partners involved.

Further suitable buffer time should be factored in for checking printed samples ahead of each print run: the correct rendition of text, logos, and graphics/colours should be checked, as well as the quality of the folding in the case of the brochures.

The Consortium now has general-purpose brochures, posters, stand-alone banners, and tote bags ready for any event.

Partners now have all the templates they might need to start planning the printing of their own posters and brochures.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL